

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added Course 2019-20 academic year for BPT

YOGA

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added course
on
YOGA

for BPT 2017 batch

Course duration
10 weeks (40 hours)

Course Objectives

1. To provide the necessary knowledge of practice of yoga so that the students learn to practice and also to teach yoga to all age groups for promoting their health and effectiveness.
2. To provide the necessary knowledge and skills of performing Asanas, Mudras, Bandas, Pranayama and meditative postures.

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Course period	From July till September 2019, during 5 th semester (10 weeks)
Duration	40 hours (4 hours/week)
Language of instruction	English
Participants	BPT 3 rd year undergraduates (2017 batch)

Course Objectives:

1. To provide the necessary knowledge of the theory and practice of yoga so that the students learn to practice and also to teach yoga to all age groups for promoting their health and effectiveness.
2. To provide the necessary knowledge of Asanas, Mudras, Bandas, Pranayama and meditative postures.

COURSE OUTLINE		
MOD	TOPIC	HOURS
1	Introduction: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Yoga philosophy, origin of Yoga, principles and importance of yoga.• Basic yogic principles: Stages of yoga.• Types of yoga: Hatha Yoga, Raja Yoga, Laya Yoga, Bhakti Yoga, Ashtanga Yoga, Karma Yoga.	3
2	Effects of yoga on various systems: Musculoskeletal, Neuro, Cardiovascular, metabolic, Gastrointestinal, mental and reproductive systems.	4
3	Yoga Asana: Principles, muscle work and kinematics; Relevance of asana to exercise. Types of asana: <ol style="list-style-type: none">Forward Bending Asanas: Uttanasana, Padahasthasana, Prasarirapaduttanasana, Janusirsasana, Triangamukhiekapadapaschimottanasana, Paschimottanasana, Ardhapadmabaddapaschimottanasana.Back Bending Asanas: Salabhasana, Bhujangasana, Ustrasana, Dhanurasana, Urdhvhadhanurasana, Chakrasana.Standing Asanas: Suryanamaskar, Utkatasana, Urdhvahasthasana, Urdhvhadhanguliasana, Prasarirapadahasthasana, Trikonasana, Parsavakonasana, Ardhashchandrasana, Adhomukhasavanasana, Veerabhadrasana.Inversions: Sirsasana, Sarvangasana, Halasana.Twisting Asanas: Floor twisting, Chair twisting, Standing twisting.Sitting Asanas: Sukhasana, Bhaddakonasana, Padmasana, Ardhapadmasana, Veerasana, Dandasana, Upavistakonasana.Supine Asanas: Suptapadangusthasana, Sukhsamvyayamas.Restorative Asanas: Suptaveerasana, Suptabhaddakonasana, Setubandhasarvangasana, SavasanaTratakas: Visual Training Asanas	25
4	Pranayama, Bandhas and Mudras: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Pranayama definition, phases, types and principles (Ujjai Pranayama, Anulomvilom, Bhastrika, Bhramri, Nadishodhan, Kapalbharti, Omkar, Suryabhedana, Chandrabhedana).• Difference between pranayama and deep breathing.• Meaning of Bandhas and mudras, physical effects, types.	5
5	Dhyana: Meaning and benefits of Dhyana; Intellectual concentration vs dhyana.	3

References:

1. Sri G Dayanidi & Smt. Reena Dayanidy. Principles and methods of yoga practices. ICYER.

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CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This is to certify that

ALBIN MANI (PT2017001)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from July to September 2019

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
Assistant Professor
Course Instructor

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean
College of Physiotherapy

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This is to certify that

ALEESHA ASBIN M S (PT2017002)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from July to September 2019

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
Assistant Professor
Course Instructor

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Dean
College of Physiotherapy

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This is to certify that

ANSARI NIKHAT PARVEEN MOHD MUSTAFA

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from July to September 2019

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
Assistant Professor
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This is to certify that

ANUSHREE M G (PT2017005)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from July to September 2019

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

ASHVITHA (PT2017008)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from July to September 2019

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This is to certify that

BENADE SONIYA SANJU (PT2017010)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from July to September 2019

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

BHOSLE SNEHAL RAVINDRA (PT2017011)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from July to September 2019

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

BRAYAN SHARON (PT2017012)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from July to September 2019

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

CHODE NAYANA SRINIVAS (PT2017013)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from July to September 2019

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

CHORDIYA MANJU VIJAYKUMAR (PT2017014)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from July to September 2019

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

HARSH JITENDRA RAVAL (PT2017016)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from July to September 2019

Total Hours- 40

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HARSHITHA (PT2017017)

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This is to certify that

HELAN MARIA SHAJI (PT2017018)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from July to September 2019

Total Hours- 40

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This is to certify that

JAVIYA NIRALIBEN HITENDRABHAI (PT2017019)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from July to September 2019

Total Hours- 40

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This is to certify that

JESLIN (PT2017020)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from July to September 2019

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This is to certify that

KALSHETTY PRIYANKA NAGESH (PT2017023)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from July to September 2019

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

KAMERKAR KUNJAL VINOD (PT2017024)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from July to September 2019

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

KAPADIA MAHI RAKESH (PT2017025)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
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Total Hours- 40

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This is to certify that

KARKERA RIA UMESH (PT2017026)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
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Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This is to certify that

RAHUL R (PT2017028)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
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Total Hours- 40

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This is to certify that

RESHMA MARIA JOSE (PT2017030)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
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Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

SATHEESHA KUMAR K (PT2017032)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
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Total Hours- 40

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This is to certify that

SELMAN P (PT2017033)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
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Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

SHAHANA SHIRIN CH (PT2017034)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
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Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
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This is to certify that

SHEETAL (PT2017035)

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This is to certify that

SIDARTH O (PT2017036)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
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This is to certify that

SUPRIYA G (PT2017037)

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This is to certify that

WALARISHA SHULLAI (PT2017041)

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